

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cream by Using Butterfly Pea Flower

Shradha Amraj*, Anil Sori, Tulsidas Nimbekar

Shri Laxmanrao Mankar Institute Pharmacy Amgaon 441902.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 May 2025

Keywords:

Herbal cream, Butterfly pea flower, Aloe barbadensis (gel), Rich in antioxidant.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15407112

ABSTRACT

The butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) is rich in anthocyanins, flavonoids and antioxidant, making it a valuable ingredient in skincare formulation. This study focuses on the development and evaluation of a topical cream containing butterfly pea flower extract for its potential benefits in skin brightening, anti-aging, and antioxidant activity. The extract was incorporated into a stable oil-in-water emulsion and assessed for physicochemical properties, stability, pH, spreadability, and user acceptability. In vitro antioxidant assays indicated significant free radical scavenging activity, suggesting protective effects against oxidative stress. The cream demonstrated good skin compatibility and moisturizing effects during a short-term application study. Natural remedies are general considered more acceptable and safer than synthetic alternatives. The primary objective of our study is to develop a herbal cream with multiple benefits, including moisturizing the skin, reducing acne and irritation, and alleviating various skin condition such as eczema, psoriasis, dryness, wrinkles, and rashes. Additionally, the cream aims to enhance the natural glow of the skin. The quality evaluation of formulation F1 to F3 was conducted based on various parameters such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, and phase separation. Among these, formulation cream.

INTRODUCTION

Cream is defined as semisolid emulsion that can be either oil in water (o/w) or water in oil (w/o) type. These are semisolid emulsion for external use only. Butterfly pea flower cream is a luxurious skincare product infused with the natural power of *Clitoria ternatea*, commonly known as butterfly

pea flower, Renowned for its vibrant blue color and rich antioxidant content, this botanical ingredient helps to soothe, rejuvenate, and protect the skin from environmental stressors. With its anti-inflammatory and anti-aging properties. They are helps to improve elasticity, reduce fine lines, and soothe irritation. With its gentle, botanical formula, butterfly pea flower cream is ideal for

*Corresponding Author: Shradha Amraj

Address: Shri Laxmanrao Mankar Institute Pharmacy Amgaon 441902

Email : amrajshradha0@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

those seeking a natural and effective way to maintain healthy, radiant skin.

Fig. Herbal Cream

3.Plant Profile:

Clitoria ternatea are called as Asian pigeon wings or butterfly pea or blue bell or blue pea or cordofan pea or Darwin's pea, IT is a species belonging to Fabaceae family having Synonyms:Clitoris princissae. In Indian Ayurveda it is commonly known by the Aparajita.

Fig. Clitoria Ternatea

Synonyms:

Butterfly pea, Bluebell vine, Asian pigeonwings, blue pea, Telangflowers. Clitoria albiflora Mattie,

Clitoria bracteates Pair, Clitoria zanzibarensis Vatke.

Biological source:

It is obtained from dried flowers or fresh flowers, leaves of Clitoria ternatea.

Phytoconstituents:

It contains tannis, phlobatannins, carbohydrates, saponins, flavonoid. protein alkaloids, anthocyanins.

5.2 Morphological distribution:

Color: Deep blue, white

Order: Fabales

Shape: Elliptic- oblong

Size: 4 to 5 cm in length.

Taste: Very mild, slightly earthy taste, similar to green tea

Scientific/Taxonomical:

Table No.02 Taxonomical classification.

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Super division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Fables
Family	Fabaceae
Subfamily	Faboideae
Genus	Clitoria
Species	Clitoria ternatea L.

Vernacular Name:

English: Butterfly pea, blue pea

Indononesia: Kembang telang

Indian: Kajroti

Bali: Bunga celeng

Brazil: Cunha
 Hindi: Aparajita
 Marathi: Gokarna
 Gujrati: Gorani

After maceration, filter the extract using cheesecloth, a fine sieve, or filter paper to remove the solid residues

4. MATERIALS AND METHOD:

4.1 MATERIAL:

- Dried or fresh butterfly pea flowers
- Distilled water
- Glass or stainless-steel container
- Stirring rod
- Filter or cheesecloth
- Storage bottle

5. METHOD:

1. Extraction process:

Prepare the flowers:

Use fresh or dried butterfly pea flowers. If using fresh flowers, Rinse them to improve dirt and impurities.

ii. Maceration (Soaking):

Add the flowers to a glass or stainless-steel container. Pour distilled water over the flowers in 10 to 20 ml of water per gram of flowers. Stir the mixture gently to ensure even contact.

iii. Extraction Time and Temperature:

Let the mixture sit at room temperature (25 -30°C) for 6-24 hours. For better efficiency, gentle stirring every few hours helps release the anthocyanins. Higher temperature (40-50°C) can improve extraction efficiency but may degrade anthocyanins over time.

vi. Filtration:

v. Concentration:

If more concentrated extract is needed, evaporate some of the water using a low-temperature method like vacuum evaporation or freeze -drying.

vi. Storage:

Store the extract in an airtight dark-colored container to protect it from light degradation.

Refrigerate(4°C) to extend shelf life

Fig. Extraction of butterfly pea flowers

6. Excipient And Herbal Ingredients with Their Role:

Sr.no	Ingredient	Role
1	Butterfly pea flower extract	Antioxidants, Anti-inflammatory.
2	Aloe vera gel	Antiaging, anti-inflammatory, moisturizer, reduce acne and pimple.
3	Beeswax	Emulsifying agent, stabilizer and gives thickness to the cream
4	Liquid paraffin	Lubricant agent
5	Borax	Alkaline agent which reacts with emulsifying agent to form soap
6	Methyl paraben	Preservative
7	Rose oil	Fragrance

7. Formulation Of Herbal Cream:

Heat liquid paraffin and beeswax in borosilicate glass beaker at 75°C. It maintains that heating temperature. (oil phase)

In another beaker, dissolve borax, methylparaben in distilled water and heat.

This beaker to 75°C to dissolve borax and methylparaben and to get a clear solution. (Aqueous phase)

Then slowly add this aqueous phase to heated oily phase.

Add a measured amount of aloe vera.

Add measured amount of butterfly pea flower extract.

Stir vigorously until forms smooth cream.

Add few drops of rose oil as a fragrance.

7.1 Formula Table

Sr no	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3
1	Butterfly Pea Flower Extract	1.5ml	1ml	1ml
2	Aloe Vera gel	1.5ml	1ml	1ml
3	Beeswax	3g	3.5g	3.2g
4	Liquid paraffin	10ml	15ml	12ml
5	Borax	0.2g	0.4g	0.3g
6	Methyl paraben	0.02g	0.04g	0.03g

Fig. Final product

8. Evaluation Of Cream:

1. Appearance:

The appearance of the butterfly pea flower cream was examined after application, noting characteristic such as color, texture, odor, state.

2. PH:

A small amount of the cream was applied to PH paper and compared against a standard pH color chart to estimate the pH level.

3. Irritancy:

A 1 cm² area was marked on the dorsal surface of the left hand. A cream was then applied to the marked area, and the time of application was recorded. The site was observed for signs of irritancy, erythema, and edema at regular intervals

for up to 24 hours. Any changes or reactions were documented accordingly. (table)

4.Washability:

A small amount of cream was applied to the hand, and then it was washed off with tap water.

5.Greasiness:

The cream was applied to the skin surface as a smear, and it was observed whether the smear exhibited an oily or greasy texture

6.Viscosity:

Viscosity of cream was measured using Brookfield viscometer at 25°C, with spindle No.63 at 2.5 RPM.

7.Spreadability:

Spreadability was evaluated for all three formulation F1, F2, and F3. The less time it takes for the two slides to separate, the better the spreadability.

Phytochemical Test:

Fig. Phytochemical Test

Detection of Alkaloids:

1.Mayer's Test:

The reagent used in this test is Mayer's reagent, which is solution of potassium mercuric iodide. To perform the test, a few drops of Mayer's reagent are added to the extract being tested. A positive result is indicated by the formation of white- or cream-colored precipitates.

2.Wagner's Test

The reagent used in this test is Wagner's reagent, which is solution of iodine in potassium iodide. To perform the test, a few drops of Mayer's reagent are added to the extract being tested. A positive result is indicated by the formation of Reddish-brown colored precipitates.

Detection of Anthocyanins:

1.pH-dependent color change test:

Add few drops of sodium hydroxide solution to the extract. A positive result is indicated by a color change from blue to green or yellow.

Detection of Terpenoids:

1.Salkowski Test:

Add few drops of chloroform and sulfuric acid to the extract. A positive result is indicated by the formation of a reddish-brown color.

Detection of Flavonoids:

1.Akaline Reagent test:

Add few drops of 1ml to the flower extract. To observed the color change. Then add a few drops of dilute HCL.A positive result indicated by intense yellow color that turns colorless on addition of HCL indicates the presence of flavonoids.

9.RESULT:

Evaluation Of Cream:**1. Appearance:**

The appearance of the butterfly pea flower cream was examined after application, noting characteristic such as color, texture, odor, state.

2. PH:

A small amount of the cream was applied to PH paper and compared against a standard pH color chart to estimate the pH level.

Sr. No	Formulation	PH
1.	F1	6
2.	F2	6
3.	F3	6

3. Irritancy:

A 1 cm² area was marked on the dorsal surface of the left hand. A cream was then applied to the marked area, and the time of application was recorded. The site was observed for signs of irritancy, erythema, and edema at regular intervals for up to 24 hours. Any changes or reactions were documented accordingly. According to the results all the three formulation that is F1H, F2H and F3H showed no sign of irritancy, erythema and edema.

Sr. No	Formulation	Irritant effect	Erythema	Edema
1.	F1	Nil	Nil	Nil
2.	F2	Nil	Nil	Nil
3.	F3	Nil	Nil	Nil

3. Washability:

A small amount of cream was applied to the hand, and then it was washed off with tap water. All three formulation were easily washable.

Sr. No.	Formulation	Wash ability
1.	F1	Easily washable
2.	F2	Easily washable
3.	F3	Easily washable

4. Greasiness:

The cream was applied to the skin surface as a smear, and it was observed whether the smear exhibited an oily or greasy text.

Sr. No.	Formulation	Greasiness
1.	F1	Non-greasy
2.	F2	Non-greasy

3.	F3	Non-greasy
----	----	------------

5. Viscosity:

Viscosity of cream was measured using Brookfield viscometer at of 25°C using spindle No.63 at 2.5 RPM. According to the results all the three-formulation showed adequate viscosity.

Sr. No	Formulation	Viscosity
1.	F1	20108
2.	F2	11018
3.	F3	18820

6. Spreadability:

Spreadability was evaluated for all three formulation F1, F2, and F3. The less time it takes for the two slides to separate, the better the spreadability. According to statement F2 had been spreadability.

Sr. No	Formulation	Time(sec)	Spreadability
1.	F1	7	Good
2.	F2	5	Excellent
3.	F3	6	Good

10.CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, butterfly pea flower cream is a skincare product that harnesses the benefits of butterfly pea flower extract, known for its antioxidant anti-aging, and soothing properties, when infused into a cream, it helps hydrates, rejuvenate, and protect the skin. The cream is often rich in natural ingredients like plant-based oils and aloe vera gel, which contribute to its moisturizing and smoothing effects. Regular use of butterfly pea flower cream may promote a healthier, more radiant complexion while offering potential anti-inflammatory benefits.

HOW TO CITE: Shradha Amraj*, Anil Sori, Tulsidas Nimbekar, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Cream by Using Butterfly Pea Flower, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 2250-2256
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15407112>

REFERENCES

1. R.N. Shah, B.M. Methal, 2006 A Handbook of Cosmetic, Vallabh Prakashan.
2. Nikhil Nitin Navindgikar, K.A. Kamalapurkar, Prashant S. Chavan. 2020.
3. Ashwini S. Dhase, Somishwar S. Khadbadi and Shweta S. Saboo.
4. Kirtikar KR and Basu BD 1980.
5. In vitro cell. Dev. Biol. Plant 43:144148 Chang C, Yang M, Wen H & Chem J 2002.
6. Gupta, Girish & Chahal, Jagbir & Bhatia, Manisha.2010.
7. Lachman L, Lieberman H, Kanig J. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy.1991.
8. Loden M. Role of skin care in maintaining barrier function. Dermatol Ther. 2003.
9. Surya Prabha, Matangi, Santhosh Aruna. Mamidi, Gulshan Raghavamma Rama rao Nadendla.2020.
10. Akash S. Mali, Karekar P, Yadav A.V.2015.

